

Understanding the Influence of Spirituality and Meaning in Life on Stress Coping: A Study among the Residents of Shimla

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For many people, life seems very fast-paced and difficult these days. Stress is a normal part of daily life because people frequently have to manage many duties, expectations, and uncertainties at once. Understanding what actually keeps people mentally strong becomes very important in such situations. In view of this, the present research aims to find out how certain internal variables such as spirituality and meaning in life, affect an individual's ability to cope with stress. One hundred Shimla people between the ages of 18 to 50 took part in the survey. Spirituality, Meaning in life and ways to cope with stress were examined using standardized questionnaires. The outcome showed something very interesting. While there was certainly a positive relationship between spirituality and coping, it was not of statistical significance. But there was a significant and evident correlation between having a meaning in life and becoming ready to handle things well. This means that having a ruling alone may not be enough; what contributes most is the degree to which a person believes that their life has a purpose and direction (Frankl, 1963; Steger et al., 2006). Based on the study, spirituality may help people to cope with stress in a more indirect way, but meaning in life plays a more active role (Park, 2010; Krok, 2015).

Keywords: Spirituality, meaning in life, stress coping, purpose, psychological well-being

If we look around today, it is clear that stress has become a common part of today's world (Carver, 1997). People face difficulties all the time, whether they are related to personal relationships, financial concerns, employment insecurity, or academic pressure. Some people are pretty good at managing stress, while others find it to be too much for them. This difference raises the important issue of why some people are better at coping than others. In the past, psychologists mainly studied the impact of stress on the body and mind. But the focus is now on figuring out what makes people resilient in the face of stress (Park, 2010). Because positive psychology focuses on human characteristics instead of simply issues, it becomes important in this situation. Spirituality and Meaning in life are the two major benefits that have caught notice. While it is actually much broader, spirituality is frequently interpreted incorrectly as being the same as religion (Pargament, 1997). It includes a sense of unity, inner calmness, and belief in something greater than oneself (Emmons, 1999). Religion can serve as the basis for some, while nature, ethics, or reflection may be the source for others. On the other side, having a sense of meaning in life defines what gives life meaning. It is an important understanding to

note that actions are crucial, that life has a purpose, and that our experiences have significance (Frankl, 1963). Shimla offers a unique background for this research. It is a city where people go about their daily lives, as well as being a tourist attraction. That is why understanding stress includes not only what is going on in an individual's present surroundings but also how that person interprets it. When two people face the same issue, one can stay calm while the other becomes extremely nervous. This mainly depends on their viewpoint on life and thought (Park, 2010). During times of difficulty, spirituality can help people feel a little more at peace (Pargament, 1997). It gives you a feeling of comfort, like the knowledge that you are not alone or that there is greater power at work. Some people receive this through their faith, whereas others may receive it from their principles, nature, or just simple reflection (Frankl, 1963; Park, 2010; Steger, 2012). It can make problems look lighter, but it does not resolve them. Life's meaning works a bit differently. It inspires individuals to keep going. Individuals do not give up easily when they feel that their life has meaning (Frankl, 1963; Steger, Frazier, Oishi, & Kaler, 2006; Park, 2010). Even if situations get difficult, people make an attempt to do things well because they feel that they are working toward something important. This helps manage the effects of stress well (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984; Park, 2010; Steger et al., 2006). These two things are also connected. Spirituality often supports people in finding meaning in their lives. In addition, individuals feel safer and more logical as long as they feel their life has a purpose. If taken together, they enhance one's inner power and strength. This becomes even more interesting in a town like Shimla. People still stick to customs, surroundings are even more at peace and there is a very close connection with nature. People might feel more comfortable and at ease; as a result, life here is also changing at the same time. Like any other metropolis, economic strain and other current problems. This mixture is what makes it essential to fully understand how people manage stress. Do

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they rely more on their beliefs? Or do they benefit more from their sense of purpose? So, this study aims to figure out specific ways in which spirituality and life's purpose aid normal people in handling stress. The main aim of this study is to understand what is the thing which helps people to deal better with day-to-day life, rather than just only looking at stress.

Review of Literature

By looking at the past research, it is very clear that both spirituality and meaning in life are the most important parts for mental health regulations, but it is true that they do not work in the same way. Even though both of the aspects are connected to how people should deal with stress, they seem to support the coping strategies in different ways. So, spirituality, for example, can be seen as helpful when people are going through difficult times. According to Pargament (1997), it can provide a sense of comfort and help them understand what is happening in their lives. It can also create a feeling of not being alone. In the same manner, Wachholtz and Pearce (2009) found that practices like prayer and meditation can reduce stress, even if things stay the same. At the same time, it is not always clear that spirituality serves as a direct link between spirituality and direct coping. According to Szczesniak et al. (2020), spirituality may shape the way people deal with handling stress rather than directly lowering it. So, just having spiritual beliefs will not always be enough; it highly depends on how people actually use and apply them in their daily lives. Reynolds et al. (2016) also found that positive coping, like having a sense of hope and trust, can help, but negative feelings, like having doubt can increase stress. On the other hand, meaning in life seems to play a more direct role in coping with stress. Frankl (1963) believed that having meaning in life is an important part of human life and helps individuals to deal with even more difficult situations. In a similar way, Steger et al. (2006) found that people who feel their life has a purpose usually have better mental health. When someone knows what they are working towards, they tend to stay more motivated and better able to face problems. Prabu, Bhuvaneshwari, and Veeramani (2025) also support that having a strong sense of meaning in life is connected with a better sense of purpose and helps individuals to deal with challenges more effectively. It is also important to look at how spirituality and meaning in life are connected to each other. Emmons (1999) suggested that spirituality can help individuals to search for their beliefs and meaning. George and Park (2016) also explained that people develop their sense of meaning and beliefs in a very simple way, which indicates that spirituality may give direction, while meaning in life helps people in everyday decisions. This concept becomes even more important in the Indian population, where spirituality is already linked with everyday life through different traditions and practices. For example, studies related to Devta culture in Himachal Pradesh (2020) show that people are more inclined to turn to spiritual belief and practices whenever they are making decisions or dealing with any stressful situations. Still, even in such situations, it is not only spirituality that alone makes a difference, but it's also the people who help in adding meaning to a person's life. Now, overall past studies show that spirituality does help by providing comfort and support, but meaning in life seems to have a bigger role in how people manage stress. That is why it is very important to study both of the aspects together, especially in real-life situations such as Shimla.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the level of spirituality among the residents of Shimla.
- To assess the level of meaning in life among the residents of Shimla.
- To examine the relationship between spirituality and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- To examine the relationship between meaning in life and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- To investigate the combined effect of spirituality and meaning in life on stress coping among the residents of Shimla.

Hypotheses of the Study

Based on the stated objectives of the present study, which aim to explore the role of spirituality and meaning in life in stress coping, the following null and alternative hypotheses were developed.

Null Hypotheses (H_0)

The null hypotheses assume that there is no significant relationship or predictive influence among the variables and that any observed differences may be due to chance.

- H_{01} : There is no statistically significant relationship between spirituality and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- H_{02} : There is no statistically significant relationship between meaning in life and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- H_{03} : Spirituality and meaning in life do not significantly predict stress coping among the residents of Shimla.

Alternative Hypotheses (H_1)

The alternative hypotheses propose that meaningful relationships and predictive effects exist among the variables, as supported by theoretical and empirical evidence.

- H_{04} : There is a statistically significant positive relationship between spirituality and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- H_{05} : There is a statistically significant positive relationship between meaning in life and stress coping among the residents of Shimla.
- H_{06} : Spirituality and meaning in life jointly and significantly predict stress coping among the residents of Shimla.

Method

Participants

The study included 100 participants, comprising 50 males and 50 females, including, aged 18-50 years, all of whom were residents of Shimla. Participants were selected using convenience sampling.

Research Design

A quantitative and correlational approach was used, as the study aimed to understand relationships rather than cause and effect.

Measures

Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS): The Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWBS) was developed by Paloutzian and Ellison in 1982 to assess an individual's level of spiritual well-being, focusing on both religious and existential aspects of spirituality. It consists of 20 items that are related on a 6-point Likert scale, and the total score ranges from 20 to 120, where higher scores indicate a greater level of spiritual well-being. This scale has shown strong internal

consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.89 to 0.94, indicating high reliability. In terms of validity, the SWBS demonstrates strong construct and convergent validity, making it a widely used and psychometrically sound instrument in psychological and health related research.

Meaning in Life Questionnaire (MLQ): The Meaning in Life Questionnaire (MLQ) was developed by Steger, Frazier, Oishi, and Kaler in 2006 to measure two key dimensions of meaning in life, namely the presence of meaning and search for meaning. The questionnaire contains 10 items that are rated on a 7-point Likert scale, and it is divided into two subscales, each consisting of five items, with scores ranging from 5 to 35 for each dimension. The MLQ has demonstrated good reliability, with Cronbach's alpha values between 0.81 and 0.91, indicating acceptable to string internal consistency. It also shows strong construct, convergent, and discriminant validity, confirming that it effectively measures the intended psychological and constructs related to meaning in life.

Brief COPE Inventory (Shorter Version): The Brief COPE Inventory, developed by Carver in 1997, is widely used instrument designed to assess a variety of coping strategies that individuals use in response to stress. It consists of 28 items that are rated on a 4-point Likert scale and is structured into 14 subscales, each containing two items, with subscale scores ranging from 2 to 8. The reliability of the

Brief COPE varies across its subscales, with Cronbach's alpha values typically ranging from 0.50 to 0.90, reflecting moderate to good internal consistency depending on the coping dimension being measured. In terms of validity, the instrument demonstrates good construct and criterion validity, supporting its usefulness in both clinical and research settings for understanding coping behaviors.

Procedure

The participants were first informed about the study and purpose of the test was explained to them in simple terms. After they agreed to take part, they were asked to complete the questionnaires. Responses were collected online via digital platforms. They were already informed that their information and all the responses would remain confidential. Once all the data is collected, it is arranged and analysed for further studies.

Statistical Analysis

Basic statistics were used to understand the overall pattern of responses. Correlation was used to see relationships between variables, and regression was used to understand their combined effect.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics (N=100)

Variable	Type	Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Minimum	Maximum
Spirituality	Independent Variable	60.45	3.552	52	70
Meaning in Life	Independent Variable	38.40	5.608	27	50
Stress Coping	Dependent Variable	23.61	5.628	11	40

As shown in Table 1, the findings show that spirituality had a high mean ($M=60.45$, $SD=3.552$), indicating that most of the participants had high and similar levels of spirituality. The modest mean ($M=38.40$, $SD=5.608$) for meaning in life showed higher variation among people. In addition, stress coping was moderate ($M=23.61$, $SD=5.628$), suggesting that individuals manage stress in different ways. While meaning and coping vary among people, spirituality was typically more reliable.

Table 2

Correlation Analysis (N=100)

Variables	r	p
Spirituality - Stress Coping	0.112	.267
Meaning in Life - Stress Coping	0.352	<.001

As shown in Table 2, stress coping and spirituality had a weak and non-significant connection ($r=0.112$, $p=.267$). On the opposite hand, stress coping was significantly positively correlated with meaning in life ($r=0.352$, $p<.001$). Thus, people who have a greater sense of purpose typically manage stress better.

As shown in Table 3, the overall model explained roughly by 13.9% of the variance in stress coping ($R^2 = 0.139$) and was significant ($F = 7.837$, $p = .001$). Spirituality was not significant ($\beta = 0.123$, $p = .196$), whereas meaning in life was a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.356$, $p < .001$). This indicates that a person's sense of meaning

in life is a more significant predictor of stress management.

Table 3

Multiple Regression Analysis (N=100)

Predictor	B	SE B	β	t	p
Spirituality	-	-	0.123	-	.196
Meaning in Life	-	-	0.356	-	<.001

Note. $N = 100$. β = standardized regression coefficient. $p < .05$ = significant

Statistic	Value
R	0.373
R^2	0.139
Adjusted R^2	0.121
F (2,97)	7.837
p	.001

Note. $p < .05$ indicates statistical significance

Discussion

This study looked at how spirituality and meaning in life are connected to the way people deal with stress. The findings showed something quite interesting. While both spirituality and meaning in life were positively related to stress coping, meaning in life had a much stronger influence. In fact, it was the only significant predictor of stress coping in this study.

This suggests that what actually helps people to manage stress is having a sense of purpose and direction in life. When people know what matters to them and feel that their lives have meaning, they are often better able to deal with challenges. They are less likely to feel completely overwhelmed when difficult situations arise. Instead, they tend to see all the problems as something that can be handled, even if the situation is difficult.

A sense of meaning can act like an inner guide. It helps people to stay focused, maintain hope, and keep going during hard times. When life feels purposeful, stressful experiences may seem more manageable because they are viewed as part of larger journey rather than as isolated setbacks.

These findings are supported by previous research. Steger et al. (2006) found that people who experience a stronger sense of meaning in life generally report better psychological well-being and are better able to adjust to challenges. Park and Baumeister (2017) also noted that meaning helps individuals make sense of their experiences and gives them a sense of direction. This idea is closely related to Viktor Frankl's view that finding meaning in one of the most important human needs, especially during times of hardship.

Spirituality showed a positive but non-significant relationship with stress coping, indicating that it did not directly predict coping in this study. However, it does not reduce its importance. Spirituality often provides comfort, hope, and sense of connection during difficult times. Its role may be more indirect. Krok (2015) suggested that spirituality supports coping by helping individuals find meaning and purpose in life. This may explain why meaning in life emerged as a stronger predictor of stress coping.

The cultural context of Shimla may be relevant. Since spirituality is widely practiced in this region, participants may have had similar levels of spirituality, limiting its ability to predict differences in coping. Overall, while spirituality offers emotional support, meaning in life appears to play a more direct role in helping individuals cope effectively with stress.

Conclusion

To conclude, the study shows that meaning in life plays a key role in helping individuals cope with stress. While spirituality is important, it seems to work more in the background. What really makes a difference is whether a person feels that their life has direction and purpose. This is important because it moves the focus to more real-life beliefs and experiences rather than only focusing on a single aspect. Helping people to find meaning in their own lives can be a really effective way to encourage better mental health.

Limitations of the Study

- The number of participants was limited
- Sampling method was not random
- Responses were self-reported

- The study was conducted at one point in time

Future Directions

In future studies, we can include a larger number of participants and can explore different locations or areas to get better results. It may also be useful to study how things change over time. Other factors, such as resilience and social support can also be added to explore more areas of study. Also, with this, practical programs and interventions can also be helpful to find meaning in their own lives.

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Received March 24, 2026

Revision received April 8, 2026

Accepted April 10, 2026